

APPROXIMATION AND ENTROPY NUMBERS OF EMBEDDINGS BETWEEN APPROXIMATION SPACES

FERNANDO COBOS¹, ÓSCAR DOMÍNGUEZ², AND THOMAS KÜHN³

ABSTRACT. We consider general linear approximation spaces X_q^b based on X and we analyse the degree of compactness of the embedding $X_q^b \hookrightarrow X$. Applications are given to periodic Besov spaces on the d -torus. We show the exact asymptotic behaviour of approximation and entropy numbers of embeddings $B_{p,q}^{s,\psi} \hookrightarrow L_p, B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma} \hookrightarrow L_p$ and $B_{p,u}^{s,\psi} \hookrightarrow B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma}$. Approximation spaces and Besov spaces and Compact embeddings and Entropy numbers and Approximation numbers

1. INTRODUCTION

The problem of compactness of embeddings between function spaces on bounded domains Ω in \mathbb{R}^d is a classical question with a long history. Many authors have studied this problem by using a variety of techniques, some of them based upon piecewise-polynomial approximation, more refined spline approximations, the Fourier-analytical approach or wavelet bases. See, for example, the books by Triebel [39, 4.10], König [24, 3.C], Edmunds and Triebel [18, 3.3] and the references given there; see also the papers by Leopold [29] and Cobos and Kühn [10]. The related question of embeddings between weighted function spaces on \mathbb{R}^d has been also extensively studied as can be seen in the papers by Haroske and Triebel [23], Kühn, Leopold, Sickel and Skrzypczak [26–28] and Haroske and Skrzypczak [21, 22]. The outcome is the description of the degree of compactness of the embeddings id in terms of the asymptotic behaviour of entropy numbers ($e_n(\text{id})$) and of approximation numbers ($a_n(\text{id})$). For the case where Ω is a bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^d with C^∞ boundary, $0 < p, q \leq \infty, s > 0$ and we consider the embedding operator id from the Besov space $B_{p,q}^s(\Omega)$ into the Lebesgue space $L_p(\Omega)$, it turns out that $a_n(\text{id})$ and $e_n(\text{id})$ behave asymptotically as $n^{-s/d}$.

In this paper we deal with periodic spaces of functions on the d -torus \mathbb{T}^d . Besides Besov spaces $B_{p,q}^s$, we also consider Besov spaces of generalized smoothness $B_{p,q}^{s,\psi}$ where $s \geq 0$ and ψ is a slowly varying function, paying special attention to the case when $s = 0$ and $\psi(t) = (1 + |\log t|)^\gamma$ that we denote by $B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma}$ (see, for example, the papers by DeVore, Riemenschneider and Sharpley [16], Caetano, Gogatishvili and Opic [5] or Cobos and Domínguez [7, 8]). Spaces $B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma}$ have only logarithmic smoothness.

Let $1 < p < \infty$. For the embedding $\text{id} : B_{p,q}^{s,\psi} \hookrightarrow L_p$ we show that the approximation and entropy numbers behave as $n^{-s/d}/\psi(n^{1/d})$. If $s = 0$ and $\psi(t) = (1 + |\log t|)^\gamma$ then the behaviour is as $(\log n)^{-(\gamma+1/q)}$ if $\gamma + 1/q > 0$, while in the limit case $\gamma = -1/q$ and $0 < q < \infty$, we derive that they behave asymptotically as $(\log \log n)^{-1/q}$. It is remarkable that when $s = 0$ the estimates do not depend

on the dimension d . We also establish sharp results on approximation and entropy numbers of embeddings $B_{p,u}^{s,\psi} \hookrightarrow B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma}$.

To establish all these estimates we follow a new approach based on the structure of $B_{p,q}^{s,\psi}$ as approximation space modeled on L_p . In fact, given an abstract approximation scheme $(X; A_n)$, we consider the approximation space X_q^b , where b is a certain sequence of positive numbers and we analyse the degree of compactness of the embedding $X_q^b \hookrightarrow X$ in terms of approximation and entropy numbers.

We work with sequences b sufficiently general such that spaces X_q^b include as particular cases classical approximation spaces X_q^α (see [4, 14, 15, 32, 34]), the more general spaces $X_q^{(\alpha,\psi)}$ (see [8, 35]), as well as limiting approximation spaces $X_q^{(0,\gamma)}$ (see [11, 12, 19]). Almira and Luther [1, 2] have also studied an extension of spaces X_q^α but our conditions on the parameters are different.

In Section 2 we introduce spaces X_q^b , we show an equivalent quasi-norm in X_q^b and a representation theorem which allows us to describe any element $f \in X_q^b$ as the sum of a series $f = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} g_j$ with $g_j \in A_{n(j)}$ for a certain sequence $(n(j))$. This result comprises several others in the literature. Namely, the representation theorems established by Pietsch [34, Theorem 3.1] for X_q^α , Cobos and Resina [12, 13] and Fehér and Grässler [19, Theorem 1] for $X_q^{(0,\gamma)}$ with $\gamma > -1/q$ and Pustylnik [35, Theorem 3.3] for $X_q^{(\alpha,\psi)}$. In addition, it gives new information for $X_q^{(0,-1/q)}$, the extreme case where $\gamma = -1/q$ and $0 < q < \infty$ which shows another jump in the scale.

In Section 3 we show a procedure to relate limiting spaces with classical spaces by making a selection in the approximation sets A_n . As a consequence, we derive the reiteration theorem and the interpolation theorem for limiting spaces $X_q^{(0,\gamma)}$ with $\gamma > -1/q$ established in [19, Theorems 2 and 5] from the corresponding results for spaces X_q^α given in [34, Theorem 3.2], [31] and [4, Korollar 2.3.1]. In the extreme case $\gamma = -1/q$ we obtain a new reiteration result using this technique. We also use this approach to derive interpolation properties of limiting spaces from the properties of spaces X_q^α .

Then, in Section 4, we work with a linear approximation scheme $(X; A_n)$, that is, we suppose that $A_n = P_n(X)$ where (P_n) is a sequence of uniformly bounded projections on X . We consider the embedding $\text{id} : X_q^b \hookrightarrow X$ and we show an upper estimate for approximation numbers and a lower estimate for entropy numbers. When X_q^b equals $X_q^{(\alpha,\psi)}$ and $\alpha > 0$, we determine the exact asymptotic behaviour of entropy and approximation numbers of the embedding. We also cover the case $X_q^b = X_q^{(0,\gamma)}$ for $\gamma \geq -1/q$, as well as some other embeddings including $\text{id} : X_u^{(\alpha,\psi)} \hookrightarrow X_q^{(0,\gamma)}$.

In the final Section 5 we apply the previous results to embeddings $B_{p,q}^{s,\psi} \hookrightarrow L_p$, $B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma} \hookrightarrow L_p$ and $B_{p,u}^{s,\psi} \hookrightarrow B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma}$ establishing the results already announced for approximation numbers and entropy numbers.

Usually one needs different tools to deal with classical spaces $B_{p,q}^s$ and with Besov spaces with smoothness close to zero, as $B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma}$ (see, for example, [9]). However, the approach that we describe here allows us to cover both cases. Other applications of the abstract results are possible. In particular they can be used to derive similar results for Besov sequence spaces.

2. APPROXIMATION SPACES

Subsequently, given two sequences $(u_n), (v_n)$ of non-negative real numbers, we write $u_n \lesssim v_n$ if there is a constant $c > 0$ such that $u_n \leq c v_n$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Notation $u_n \sim v_n$ means $u_n \lesssim v_n$ and $v_n \lesssim u_n$. A similar notation is used for quasi-norms.

Let $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ be a quasi-Banach space and let $(A_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}_0}$ be a sequence of subsets of X satisfying the following conditions

$$\begin{aligned} A_0 &= \{0\} \subseteq A_1 \subseteq \dots \subseteq A_n \subseteq \dots \subseteq X, \\ \lambda A_n &\subseteq A_n \text{ for any scalar } \lambda \text{ and any } n \in \mathbb{N}_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}, \\ A_n + A_m &\subseteq A_{n+m} \text{ for any } n, m \in \mathbb{N}_0. \end{aligned}$$

Given any $f \in X$, we put $E_0(f) = \|f\|_X$ and

$$E_n(f) = E_n(f)_X = \inf\{\|f - g\|_X : g \in A_n\}, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Let $b = (b_n)$ be a sequence of positive numbers with $b_1 = 1$ and let $0 < q \leq \infty$. We assume that

$$(1) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n^q n^{-1} = \infty \text{ if } q < \infty \text{ and } \sup_{n \geq 1} \{b_n\} = \infty \text{ if } q = \infty.$$

The *approximation space* $X_q^b = (X; A_n)_q^b$ consists of all $f \in X$ which have a finite quasi-norm

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_{X_q^b} &= \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (b_n E_{n-1}(f))^q n^{-1} \right)^{1/q} \quad \text{if } 0 < q < \infty, \\ \|f\|_{X_q^b} &= \sup_{n \geq 1} \{b_n E_{n-1}(f)\} \quad \text{if } q = \infty. \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to check that if (1) does not hold then we are in the trivial case where $X = X_q^b$ with equivalence of quasi-norms. Clearly $X_q^b \hookrightarrow X$ where \hookrightarrow means continuous embedding. Moreover, if $b_n \sim h_n$ then $X_q^b = X_q^h$ with equivalence of quasi-norms.

Subsequently, we suppose that there is a sequence of positive integers $1 = n(0) < n(1) < \dots < n(j) < \dots$ and an increasing sequence of positive numbers $1 = \varphi(0) < \varphi(1) < \dots < \varphi(j) < \dots$ such that

$$(2) \quad \begin{cases} \sum_{k=n(j)+1}^{n(j+1)} b_k^q k^{-1} \sim \varphi(j+1)^q & \text{if } q < \infty, \\ \max_{n(j)+1 \leq k \leq n(j+1)} b_k \sim \varphi(j+1) & \text{if } q = \infty. \end{cases}$$

We suppose also that there are $N \in \mathbb{N}$ and constants $1 < K_1 < K_2$ such that

$$(3) \quad K_1 \leq \frac{\varphi(j+1)}{\varphi(j)} \leq K_2, j \geq N.$$

In particular, $\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \varphi(j) = \infty$.

Next we show other equivalent quasi-norm in X_q^b .

Lemma 2.1. *Under the assumptions (1), (2) and (3) the quasi-norm of X_q^b is equivalent to*

$$\|f\|_{X_q^b}^{\diamond} = \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\varphi(j) E_{n(j)-1}(f))^q \right)^{1/q}$$

(the sum should be replaced by the supremum if $q = \infty$).

Proof. Suppose $0 < q < \infty$. According to (2), (3) and the fact that $(E_n(f))$ is non-increasing, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_{X_q^b} &= \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=n(j)}^{n(j+1)-1} \frac{(b_k E_{k-1}(f))^q}{k} \right)^{1/q} \\ &\leq \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} E_{n(j)-1}(f)^q \sum_{k=n(j)}^{n(j+1)-1} \frac{b_k^q}{k} \right)^{1/q} \\ &\lesssim \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} E_{n(j)-1}(f)^q \varphi(j+1)^q \right)^{1/q} \\ &\lesssim \|f\|_{X_q^\diamond}. \end{aligned}$$

Conversely, using (2), we derive

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_{X_q^b} &= \left(\|f\|_X^q + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=n(j)+1}^{n(j+1)} \frac{(b_k E_{k-1}(f))^q}{k} \right)^{1/q} \\ &\gtrsim \left(\|f\|_X^q + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} E_{n(j+1)-1}(f)^q \varphi(j+1)^q \right)^{1/q} \\ &= \|f\|_{X_q^\diamond}. \end{aligned}$$

The case $q = \infty$ is similar. □

In what follows we also assume

$$(4) \quad \begin{cases} \text{for any } n \in \mathbb{N}, A_n \text{ is a linear subspace of } X, \\ \text{or} \\ \text{for any } r \in \mathbb{N}, \text{ we have that } \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} n(j) \leq n(r). \end{cases}$$

The following result shows a characterization for elements of X_q^b as sums of series with terms in the sets $A_{n(j)}$. Recall that we may assume without loss of generality that $\|\cdot\|_X$ is a p -norm with $0 < p < q$ (see [25, 15.10] or [24, Proposition 1.c.5]).

Theorem 2.2. *Assume that (1), (2), (3) and (4) hold. Let $f \in X$. Then $f \in X_q^b$ if and only if there is a representation $f = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} g_j$ (convergence in X) with $g_j \in A_{n(j)}$ and $(\varphi(j)\|g_j\|_X) \in \ell_q$. Furthermore,*

$$\|f\|_{X_q^*} = \inf \left\{ \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\varphi(j)\|g_j\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q} : g_j \in A_{n(j)} \text{ and } f = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} g_j \right\}$$

is an equivalent quasi-norm on X_q^b .

Proof. Suppose $0 < q < \infty$ and let $f \in X_q^b$. Take any $\varepsilon > 0$ and for each $j \in \mathbb{N}_0$ find $f_j \in A_{n(j)}$ such that $\|f - f_j\|_X \leq (1 + \varepsilon)E_{n(j)}(f)$. Put $f_{-1} = 0$ and $g_j =$

$f_j - f_{j-1}, j \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Since $f \in X_q^b$ and (1) holds, we have that $E_n(f) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. This yields that

$$\left\| f - \sum_{j=0}^k g_j \right\|_X = \|f - f_k\|_X \leq (1 + \varepsilon)E_{n(k)}(f) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } k \rightarrow \infty.$$

Hence $f = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} g_j$ with convergence in X . Moreover,

$$\|g_j\|_X \leq c_X(\|f - f_j\|_X + \|f - f_{j-1}\|_X) \leq 2(1 + \varepsilon)c_X E_{n(j-1)}(f), j \in \mathbb{N},$$

and

$$\|g_0\|_X \leq c_X(\|f\|_X + \|f - f_0\|_X) \leq 2(1 + \varepsilon)c_X E_0(f).$$

Here c_X is the constant in the quasi-triangle inequality in X . Whence, using (3) and Lemma 2.1, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_{X_q^b}^* &\leq \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\varphi(j)\|g_j\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q} \\ &\lesssim \left((\varphi(0)E_0(f))^q + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} (\varphi(j)E_{n(j-1)}(f))^q \right)^{1/q} \\ &\lesssim \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\varphi(j)E_{n(j)-1}(f))^q \right)^{1/q} \\ &\lesssim \|f\|_{X_q^b}. \end{aligned}$$

Next we check the converse inequality. As we pointed out before, we may assume that $\|\cdot\|_X$ is a p -norm with $0 < p < q$. Let $s > 0$ such that $1/p = 1/q + 1/s$. Given any representation $f = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} g_j$ (convergence in X) with $g_j \in A_{n(j)}$ and $(\varphi(j)\|g_j\|_X) \in \ell_q$, we have by (4) that $\sum_{j=0}^r g_j \in A_{n(r+1)}, r \in \mathbb{N}$. Take any $1 < D < K_1$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} E_{n(r+1)}(f) &\leq \left\| f - \sum_{j=0}^r g_j \right\|_X = \left(\left\| \sum_{j=r+1}^{\infty} g_j \right\|_X^p \right)^{1/p} \\ &\leq \left(\sum_{j=r+1}^{\infty} \|g_j\|_X^p \right)^{1/p} = \left(\sum_{j=r+1}^{\infty} (D^j \|g_j\|_X)^p D^{-jp} \right)^{1/p} \\ &\leq \left(\sum_{j=r+1}^{\infty} (D^j \|g_j\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q} \left(\sum_{j=r+1}^{\infty} D^{-js} \right)^{1/s} \\ &= \frac{D^{-(r+1)}}{(1 - D^{-s})^{1/s}} \left(\sum_{j=r+1}^{\infty} (D^j \|g_j\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, using Lemma 2.1 and (3), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\|f\|_{X_q^s} &\sim \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\varphi(j) E_{n(j)-1}(f))^q \right)^{1/q} \\
&\leq \left(\|f\|_X^q + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\varphi(j+1) E_{n(j)}(f))^q \right)^{1/q} \\
&\lesssim \left(\|f\|_X^q + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\varphi(j) E_{n(j)}(f))^q \right)^{1/q} \\
&\lesssim \left(\|f\|_X^q + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\varphi(j) D^{-j})^q \sum_{k=j}^{\infty} (D^k \|g_k\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q} \\
&= \left(\|f\|_X^q + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (D^k \|g_k\|_X)^q \sum_{j=0}^k (\varphi(j) D^{-j})^q \right)^{1/q}.
\end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, since $D/K_1 < 1$, (3) also implies that $(\varphi(k) D^{-k})_{k \geq N}$ is increasing because

$$\frac{\varphi(k)}{D^k} \leq \frac{\varphi(k+1)}{D^{k+1}} \frac{D}{K_1} < \frac{\varphi(k+1)}{D^{k+1}}, k \geq N.$$

Moreover

$$\varphi(j) \leq K_1^{j-k} \varphi(k) \text{ for } N \leq j \leq k.$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{j=0}^k (\varphi(j) D^{-j})^q &\leq \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} (\varphi(j) D^{-j})^q + (\varphi(k) K_1^{-k})^q \sum_{j=N}^k (K_1/D)^{jq} \\
&\lesssim \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} (\varphi(j) D^{-j})^q + (\varphi(k) D^{-k})^q \\
&\lesssim (\varphi(k) D^{-k})^q.
\end{aligned}$$

Consequently, we derive that

$$\|f\|_{X_q^s} \lesssim \left(\|f\|_X^q + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\varphi(k) \|g_k\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q}.$$

Finally, since

$$1 = \varphi(0) < \varphi(N) \leq \frac{\varphi(j)}{K_1^{j-N}} \text{ for } j \geq N,$$

using Hölder inequality we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_X &\leq \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \|g_j\|_X^p \right)^{1/p} \lesssim \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\varphi(j) \|g_j\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} K_1^{-sj} \right)^{1/s} \\ &\lesssim \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\varphi(j) \|g_j\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q} \end{aligned}$$

and we conclude that $\|f\|_{X_q^b} \lesssim \|f\|_{X_q^*}^*$.

The case $q = \infty$ can be treated analogously. □

Now we give some examples.

Example 2.3. Let $b_n = n^\alpha \psi(n)$ where $\alpha > 0$ and ψ is a slowly varying function (see [17, pp. 108–109] and also [3]). We designate by $X_q^{(\alpha, \psi)}$ the approximation space generated by $b = (b_n)$. Without loss of generality we may assume that (b_n) is an increasing sequence. Let $n(j) = 2^j$ and $\varphi(j) = 2^{j\alpha} \psi(2^j)$. If $q = \infty$ we have

$$\max\{k^\alpha \psi(k) : n(j) + 1 \leq k \leq n(j+1)\} = 2^{(j+1)\alpha} \psi(2^{j+1}) = \varphi(j+1).$$

If $0 < q < \infty$, using [17, Proposition 3.4.33], we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=n(j)+1}^{n(j+1)} \frac{b_k^q}{k} &\sim \int_{2^j}^{2^{j+1}} (x^\alpha \psi(x))^q \frac{dx}{x} \sim 2^{(j+1)\alpha q} \psi(2^{j+1})^q \\ &= \varphi(j+1)^q. \end{aligned}$$

This shows that (2) holds. It is not hard to check that condition (3) is also satisfied (one may use [3, Theorem 1.5.6]). Conditions (1) and (4) are clear.

Writing down Lemma 2.1 and Theorem 2.2 for this case we recover [35, Theorems 3.2 and 3.3]. The special case $\psi(t) = 1$ for all $t > 0$ corresponds to the classical approximation spaces X_q^α , whose properties have been established in [34, Proposition 2 and Theorem 3.1]. In particular,

$$\|f\|_{X_q^\alpha} \sim \|f\|_{X_q^\alpha}^\diamond = \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (2^{j\alpha} E_{2^j-1}(f))^q \right)^{1/q}.$$

Example 2.4. Let $b_n = (1 + \log n)^\gamma$ with $\gamma \geq -1/q$ if $0 < q < \infty$ and $\gamma > 0$ if $q = \infty$. Let $X_q^{(0, \gamma)}$ be the approximation spaces generated by the sequence b . Put $\mu_j = 2^{2^j}$ and, if $\gamma > -1/q$, take $n(0) = 1, n(j) = \mu_j$ for $j \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\varphi(j) = 2^{j(\gamma+1/q)}$. Again conditions (1), (3) and (4) are clear. Also (2) holds because

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=\mu_j+1}^{\mu_{j+1}} \frac{(1 + \log k)^{\gamma q}}{k} &\sim \int_{\mu_j}^{\mu_{j+1}} (1 + \log x)^{\gamma q} \frac{dx}{x} \sim 2^{(j+1)(\gamma q+1)} \\ &= \varphi(j+1)^q. \end{aligned}$$

In this case, using Lemma 2.1 we recover [19, Lemma 1]:

$$\|f\|_{X_q^{(0, \gamma)}} \sim \|f\|_{X_q^{(0, \gamma)}}^\# = \left(\|f\|_X^q + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (2^{j(\gamma+1/q)} E_{\mu_j-1}(f))^q \right)^{1/q}.$$

Moreover, Theorem 2.2 gives the representation theorem for spaces $X_q^{(0,\gamma)}$ established in [12, Theorem 1.2], [13, Theorem 2] and [19, Theorem 1].

If $\gamma = -1/q$ and $0 < q < \infty$, we put $\varphi(j) = 2^{j/q}$, $\rho_j = 2^{\mu_j} = 2^{2^{2^j}}$, $n(0) = 1$ and $n(j) = \rho_j$, $j \in \mathbb{N}$. Conditions (1), (2), (3) and (4) are satisfied for this choice. Lemma 2.1 gives that

$$\|f\|_{X_q^{(0,-1/q)}} \sim \|f\|_{X_q^{(0,-1/q)}}^\# = \left(\|f\|_X^q + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (2^{j/q} E_{\rho_j-1}(f))^q \right)^{1/q},$$

and Theorem 2.2 produces the following result which covers a case left open in [12] and [19].

Theorem 2.5. *Let $0 < q < \infty$. The necessary and sufficient conditions for $f \in X$ to belong to $X_q^{(0,-1/q)}$ is that there exists $g_j \in A_{\rho_j}$ such that $f = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} g_j$ (convergence in X) with $(2^{j/q} \|g_j\|_X) \in \ell_q$. Moreover,*

$$\|f\|_{X_q^{(0,-1/q)}}^* = \inf \left\{ \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (2^{j/q} \|g_j\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q} : g_j \in A_{\rho_j}, f = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} g_j \right\}$$

is an equivalent quasi-norm on $X_q^{(0,-1/q)}$.

3. RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN APPROXIMATION SPACES GENERATED BY DIFFERENT APPROXIMATION FAMILIES

Let X and $(A_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}_0}$ be as in the previous section. Let again $\mu_j = 2^{2^j}$ and $\rho_j = 2^{\mu_j}$. Consider the new approximation families defined by

$$B_n = A_{2^n} \text{ if } n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ with } B_0 = \{0\}$$

and

$$D_n = A_{\mu_n} \text{ if } n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ with } D_0 = \{0\}.$$

Let $0 < q \leq \infty$ and $\gamma > -1/q$. According to Example 2.4, Lemma 2.1 and Example 2.3, we obtain

(5)

$$\begin{aligned} X_q^{(0,\gamma)} &= (X; A_n)_q^{(0,\gamma)} \\ &= \left\{ f \in X : \|f\|_{X_q^{(0,\gamma)}}^\# = \left(\|f\|_X^q + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (2^{j(\gamma+1/q)} E_{\mu_j-1}(f))^q \right)^{1/q} < \infty \right\} \\ &= (X; B_n)_q^{\gamma+1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

If $0 < q < \infty$ and $\gamma = -1/q$, then we get

(6)

$$\begin{aligned} X_q^{(0,-1/q)} &= (X; A_n)_q^{(0,-1/q)} \\ &= \left\{ f \in X : \|f\|_{X_q^{(0,-1/q)}}^\# = \left(\|f\|_X^q + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (2^{j/q} E_{\rho_j-1}(f))^q \right)^{1/q} < \infty \right\} \\ &= (X; D_n)_q^{1/q}. \end{aligned}$$

As a consequence, certain results on limiting spaces $X_q^{(0,\gamma)}$ which have direct proofs in the literature can be derived from the known results for the classical approximation spaces X_q^α . This is the case of the *reiteration formula*. It was shown by Pietsch [34, Theorem 3.2] that

$$(7) \quad (X_q^\alpha)_r^\beta = X_r^{\alpha+\beta} \text{ provided that } 0 < \alpha, \beta < \infty \text{ and } 0 < q, r \leq \infty.$$

For limiting spaces, Fehér and Grässler [19, Theorem 2] proved that

$$(8) \quad (X_q^{(0,\gamma)})_r^{(0,\delta)} = X_r^{(0,\gamma+\delta+1/q)} \text{ for } 0 < q, r \leq \infty, \gamma > -1/q \text{ and } \delta > -1/r.$$

Formula (8) follows from (7) using (5). Namely

$$\begin{aligned} (X_q^{(0,\gamma)})_r^{(0,\delta)} &= ((X; B_n)_q^{\gamma+1/q}; B_n)_r^{\delta+1/r} \\ &= (X; B_n)_r^{\gamma+1/q+\delta+1/r} \\ &= X_r^{(0,\gamma+1/q+\delta)}. \end{aligned}$$

This method allows us to treat the extreme case $\gamma = -1/q, \delta = -1/r$ which was not covered in [19, Theorem 2].

Theorem 3.1. *Let $0 < q, r < \infty$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} &(X_q^{(0,-1/q)})_r^{(0,-1/r)} \\ &= \left\{ f \in X : \|f\| = \left(\|f\|_X^r + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} ((1 + \log n)^{1/q} E_{2^n}(f))^r \frac{1}{n} \right)^{1/r} < \infty \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By (6), (7) and (5), we derive

$$\begin{aligned} &(X_q^{(0,-1/q)})_r^{(0,-1/r)} = ((X; D_n)_q^{1/q}; D_n)_r^{1/r} \\ &= (X; D_n)_r^{1/q+1/r} \\ &= (X; B_n)_r^{(0,1/q)} \\ &= \left\{ f \in X : \|f\| = \left(\|f\|_X^r + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} ((1 + \log n)^{1/q} E_{2^n}(f))^r \frac{1}{n} \right)^{1/r} < \infty \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

□

We can apply the same approach to establish *interpolation formulae*. Let (A_0, A_1) be a pair of quasi-Banach spaces, that is to say, two quasi-Banach spaces A_i which

are continuously embedded in the same Hausdorff topological vector space. The Peetre's K -functional is defined for $a \in A_0 + A_1$ by

$$K(t, a) = \inf\{\|a_0\|_{A_0} + t\|a_1\|_{A_1} : a = a_0 + a_1, a_i \in A_i\}, t > 0.$$

For $0 < q \leq \infty$ and $0 < \theta < 1$, the real interpolation space $(A_0, A_1)_{\theta, q}$ is formed by all those $a \in A_0 + A_1$ having a finite quasi-norm

$$\|a\|_{(A_0, A_1)_{\theta, q}} = \left(\int_0^\infty (t^{-\theta} K(t, a))^q \frac{dt}{t} \right)^{1/q}$$

(the integral should be replaced by the supremum if $q = \infty$).

According to a result of Peetre and Sparr [31] (see also [4, Korollar 2.3.1]), for $0 < \alpha_0 \neq \alpha_1 < \infty, 0 < r_0, r_1, q \leq \infty$ and $0 < \theta < 1$, we have

$$(9) \quad (X_{r_0}^{\alpha_0}, X_{r_1}^{\alpha_1})_{\theta, q} = X_q^\alpha$$

where $\alpha = (1 - \theta)\alpha_0 + \theta\alpha_1$.

If $0 < q, q_0, q_1 \leq \infty, \gamma_i > -1/q_i, i = 0, 1, \gamma_0 + 1/q_0 \neq \gamma_1 + 1/q_1$ and $0 < \theta < 1$, Fehér and Grässler [19, Theorem 5] proved that

$$(10) \quad (X_{q_0}^{(0, \gamma_0)}, X_{q_1}^{(0, \gamma_1)})_{\theta, q} = X_q^{(0, \gamma)}$$

where $\gamma = \gamma_0 + 1/q_0 - 1/q, 1/q_0 = (1 - \theta)/q_0 + \theta/q_1$ and $\gamma_0 = (1 - \theta)\gamma_0 + \theta\gamma_1$.

We can recover (10) from (9) by using (5):

$$\begin{aligned} (X_{q_0}^{(0, \gamma_0)}, X_{q_1}^{(0, \gamma_1)})_{\theta, q} &= ((X; B_n)_{q_0}^{\gamma_0 + 1/q_0}, (X; B_n)_{q_1}^{\gamma_1 + 1/q_1})_{\theta, q} \\ &= (X; B_n)_q^{\gamma_0 + 1/q_0 - 1/q + 1/q} \\ &= X_q^{(0, \gamma)}. \end{aligned}$$

For the extreme case $\gamma_i = -1/q_i$ we derive the following new interpolation formulae.

Theorem 3.2. *Let $0 < q_0, q_1 < \infty, 0 < \theta < 1$ and $1/q_0 = (1 - \theta)/q_0 + \theta/q_1$. Then*

$$(X_{q_0}^{(0, -1/q_0)}, X_{q_1}^{(0, -1/q_1)})_{\theta, q_0} = X_{q_0}^{(0, -1/q_0)}.$$

Furthermore, if $0 < r \neq q_0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} &(X_{q_0}^{(0, -1/q_0)}, X_{q_1}^{(0, -1/q_1)})_{\theta, r} \\ &= \left\{ f \in X : \|f\| = \left(\|f\|_X^r + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} ((1 + \log n)^{1/q_0 - 1/r} E_{2^n}(f))^r \frac{1}{n} \right)^{1/r} < \infty \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. According to (6) and (9), we get

$$\begin{aligned} (X_{q_0}^{(0, -1/q_0)}, X_{q_1}^{(0, -1/q_1)})_{\theta, q_0} &= ((X; D_n)_{q_0}^{1/q_0}, (X; D_n)_{q_1}^{1/q_1})_{\theta, q_0} \\ &= (X; D_n)_{q_0}^{1/q_0} = X_{q_0}^{(0, -1/q_0)}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, if $r \neq q_0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &(X_{q_0}^{(0, -1/q_0)}, X_{q_1}^{(0, -1/q_1)})_{\theta, r} = (X; D_n)_r^{1/q_0} \\ &= (X; B_n)_r^{(0, 1/q_0 - 1/r)} \\ &= \left\{ f \in X : \|f\| = \left(\|f\|_X^r + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} ((1 + \log n)^{1/q_0 - 1/r} E_{2^n}(f))^r \frac{1}{n} \right)^{1/r} < \infty \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Next we consider interpolation of approximation spaces generated by different quasi-Banach spaces. Let X_0, X_1 be quasi-Banach spaces with $X_1 \hookrightarrow X_0, A_n \subseteq X_1$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and suppose that the following assumption holds.

Assumption A. There exist a second approximation family $(\tilde{A}_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}_0}$ in $X_i, i = 0, 1$, and a sequence of linear operators $L_n : \tilde{A}_n \rightarrow A_n, n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, satisfying that if there are a positive constant M and a sequence $(g_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}_0}, g_n \in \tilde{A}_n$, such that

$$\|f - g_n\|_{X_0} \leq M \tilde{E}_n(f)_{X_0}$$

where $\tilde{E}_n(f)_{X_0}$ is the best approximation error of $f \in X_0$ with respect to \tilde{A}_n , then

$$\|f - L_n g_n\|_{X_i} \leq C_i E_n(f)_{X_i}, i = 0, 1.$$

Here the constants C_i depend only on M and X_i .

It was proved by DeVore and Popov [15, Theorem 2] that if the assumption A holds true for X_0 and X_1 then

$$(11) \quad ((X_0)_{q_0}^{\alpha_0}, (X_1)_{q_1}^{\alpha_1})_{\theta, q_\theta} = ((X_0, X_1)_{\theta, q_\theta})_{q_\theta}^{\alpha_\theta}$$

provided that $0 < \alpha_0, \alpha_1 < \infty, 0 < q_0, q_1 \leq \infty, 0 < \theta < 1, \alpha_\theta = (1 - \theta)\alpha_0 + \theta\alpha_1$ and $1/q_\theta = (1 - \theta)/q_0 + \theta/q_1$. We can complement (11) with the following formulae for limiting approximation spaces.

Theorem 3.3. *Let X_0, X_1 be quasi-Banach spaces such that $X_1 \hookrightarrow X_0, A_n \subseteq X_1$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and satisfying assumption A. Let $0 < \theta < 1$.*

(a) *If $0 < q_0, q_1 \leq \infty, \gamma_i > -1/q_i$ for $i = 0, 1, \gamma_\theta = (1 - \theta)\gamma_0 + \theta\gamma_1$ and $1/q_\theta = (1 - \theta)/q_0 + \theta/q_1$, then*

$$((X_0)_{q_0}^{(0, \gamma_0)}, (X_1)_{q_1}^{(0, \gamma_1)})_{\theta, q_\theta} = ((X_0, X_1)_{\theta, q_\theta})_{q_\theta}^{(0, \gamma_\theta)}.$$

(b) *If $0 < q_0, q_1 < \infty$, then*

$$((X_0)_{q_0}^{(0, -1/q_0)}, (X_1)_{q_1}^{(0, -1/q_1)})_{\theta, q_\theta} = ((X_0, X_1)_{\theta, q_\theta})_{q_\theta}^{(0, -1/q_\theta)}.$$

Proof. It is not hard to check that assumption A also holds for the approximation schemes $(X_0; B_n), (X_1; B_n)$. Whence, (5) and (11) yield

$$\begin{aligned} ((X_0)_{q_0}^{(0, \gamma_0)}, (X_1)_{q_1}^{(0, \gamma_1)})_{\theta, q_\theta} &= ((X_0; B_n)_{q_0}^{\gamma_0 + 1/q_0}, (X_1; B_n)_{q_1}^{\gamma_1 + 1/q_1})_{\theta, q_\theta} \\ &= ((X_0, X_1)_{\theta, q_\theta}; B_n)_{q_\theta}^{\gamma_\theta + 1/q_\theta} \\ &= ((X_0, X_1)_{\theta, q_\theta})_{q_\theta}^{(0, \gamma_\theta)}. \end{aligned}$$

The proof of (b) is similar but using now (6). □

4. APPROXIMATION AND ENTROPY NUMBERS OF EMBEDDINGS

Let $T \in \mathfrak{L}(V, W)$ be a bounded linear operator between the quasi-Banach spaces V, W . For $k \in \mathbb{N}$, the k -th *approximation number* $a_k(T)$ of T is given by

$$a_k(T) = \inf\{\|T - R\|_{V, W} : R \in \mathfrak{L}(V, W) \text{ with } \text{rank } R < k\}$$

where $\text{rank } R$ is the dimension of the range of R . The k -th (dyadic) *entropy number* $e_k(T) = e_k(T : V \rightarrow W)$ of T is defined as the infimum of all $\varepsilon > 0$ such that there are $w_1, \dots, w_{2^{k-1}} \in W$ with

$$T(U_V) \subseteq \bigcup_{j=1}^{2^{k-1}} (w_j + \varepsilon U_W).$$

Here U_V, U_W are the closed unit balls of V, W , respectively (see [6, 18, 33]).

Note that T is compact if and only if $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} e_k(T) = 0$. On the other hand, if $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} a_k(T) = 0$ then T is compact but there are compact operators T such that $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} a_k(T) > 0$ (see [18]). The asymptotic decay of the sequences $(e_k(T)), (a_k(T))$ can be considered as a measure of the degree of compactness of the operator T .

It follows from definitions that

$$\|T\|_{V,W} = a_1(T) \geq a_2(T) \geq \dots \geq 0 \text{ and } \|T\|_{V,W} \geq e_1(T) \geq e_2(T) \geq \dots \geq 0.$$

Moreover, entropy and approximation numbers are multiplicative, that is, for all $k, l \in \mathbb{N}$

$$a_{k+l-1}(S \circ T) \leq a_k(S)a_l(T), e_{k+l-1}(S \circ T) \leq e_k(S)e_l(T).$$

In this section we are going to establish the asymptotic decay of approximation and entropy numbers of embeddings involving approximation spaces.

In what follows we assume that $(X; A_n)$ is a *linear* approximation scheme. This means that there is a uniformly bounded sequence of linear projections P_n mapping X onto A_n . Then

$$(12) \quad \|f - P_n f\|_X \leq c E_n(f), f \in X, n \in \mathbb{N},$$

where $c = c_X[1 + \sup\{\|P_n\|_{X,X} : n \in \mathbb{N}\}]$. Note also that (4) holds.

Let

$$Q_0 = P_1 \text{ and } Q_j = P_{n(j)} - P_{n(j-1)} \text{ for } j \in \mathbb{N}.$$

For any $f \in X_q^b$, we have by (1) that $(E_n(f)) \rightarrow 0$. Then (12) yields that $(P_n f) \rightarrow f$ in X and therefore $f = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} Q_j f$ in X .

The following result can be proved by using (12) with the same arguments as in Theorem 2.2.

Theorem 4.1. *Assume that (1), (2) and (3) hold and that $(X; A_n)$ is a linear approximation scheme. Let $f \in X$. Then $f \in X_q^b$ if and only if $f = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} Q_j f$ (convergence in X) with $(\varphi(j)\|Q_j f\|_X) \in \ell_q$. Moreover,*

$$\|f\|_{X_q^b} \triangleq \|(\varphi(j)\|Q_j f\|_X)\|_{\ell_q}$$

is an equivalent quasi-norm in X_q^b .

Now we can establish the following estimates.

Theorem 4.2. *Assume that (1), (2) and (3) hold and that $(X; A_n)$ is a linear approximation scheme with $m(j) = \dim A_{n(j)}, j \in \mathbb{N}_0$. For the embedding $\text{id} : X_q^b \hookrightarrow X$ we have*

$$a_{m(j)+1}(\text{id}) \lesssim \frac{1}{\varphi(j)} \lesssim e_{m(j)+1}(\text{id}).$$

Proof. We know that $\text{id} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} Q_k$. Moreover,

$$\text{rank} \sum_{k=0}^j Q_k = \text{rank} P_{n(j)} = \dim A_{n(j)} = m(j).$$

Since we can assume without loss of generality that $\|\cdot\|_X$ is a p -norm, we get

$$\begin{aligned} a_{m(j)+1}(\text{id}) &\leq \left\| \text{id} - \sum_{k=0}^j Q_k \right\|_{X_q^b, X} = \left\| \sum_{k=j+1}^{\infty} Q_k \right\|_{X_q^b, X} \\ &\leq \left(\sum_{k=j+1}^{\infty} \|Q_k\|_{X_q^b, X}^p \right)^{1/p}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.1 implies that $\|Q_k\|_{X_q^b, X} \leq c/\varphi(k)$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Therefore, using (3), we obtain for $j \geq N$

$$\begin{aligned} a_{m(j)+1}(\text{id}) &\leq c \left(\sum_{k=j+1}^{\infty} \varphi(k)^{-p} \right)^{1/p} \\ &\leq c \frac{1}{\varphi(j+1)} \left(\sum_{k=j+1}^{\infty} K_1^{(j+1-k)p} \right)^{1/p} \\ &\lesssim \frac{1}{\varphi(j+1)}. \end{aligned}$$

This yields that $a_{m(j)+1}(\text{id}) \lesssim 1/\varphi(j)$.

Next we establish the lower estimate. Since $m(j) = \dim A_{n(j)}$, volume arguments (see [6, (1.1.10), p. 9]) show that

$$e_{m(j)+1}(\text{id} : A_{n(j)} \longrightarrow A_{n(j)}) \sim 1.$$

Consider the following commutative diagram

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X_q^b & \xrightarrow{\text{id}} & X \\ \text{id} \uparrow & & \nearrow \text{id} \\ A_{n(j)} & & \end{array}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &\lesssim e_{m(j)+1}(\text{id} : A_{n(j)} \longrightarrow A_{n(j)}) \\ &\leq 2 e_{m(j)+1}(\text{id} : A_{n(j)} \longrightarrow X) \\ &\leq 2 \|\text{id}\|_{A_{n(j)}, X_q^b} e_{m(j)+1}(\text{id} : X_q^b \longrightarrow X). \end{aligned}$$

In order to estimate $\|\text{id}\|_{A_{n(j)}, X_q^b}$ note that if f belongs to $A_{n(j)}$ then f is already a series representation as in Theorem 2.2. Hence,

$$\|f\|_{X_q^b} \lesssim \|f\|_{X_q^b}^* \leq \varphi(j) \|f\|_X.$$

Consequently,

$$e_{m(j)+1}(\text{id} : X_q^b \longrightarrow X) \gtrsim 1/\varphi(j).$$

□

The estimates in Theorem 4.2 can be improved in the important concrete cases that we discuss below, where we give the precise asymptotic behaviour for entropy and approximation numbers.

Subsequently, we suppose that there is $0 < \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$(13) \quad m(j) = \dim A_{n(j)} \sim n(j)^\lambda.$$

We write $[\cdot]$ for the greatest integer function.

Corollary 4.3. *Let $b_n = n^\alpha \psi(n)$ where $\alpha > 0$ and ψ is a slowly varying function. Assume that $(X; A_n)$ is a linear approximation scheme satisfying (13) and that $0 < q \leq \infty$. Then for the embedding $\text{id} : X_q^b \hookrightarrow X$ we have*

$$a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim \frac{1}{n^{\alpha/\lambda} \psi(n^{1/\lambda})}.$$

Proof. As we have seen in Example 2.3, in this case $\varphi(j) = 2^{j\alpha} \psi(2^j)$ and $n(j) = 2^j$. According to Theorem 4.2, we derive

$$a_{[2^{j\lambda}]+1}(\text{id}) \lesssim \frac{1}{2^{j\alpha} \psi(2^j)} \lesssim e_{[2^{j\lambda}]+1}(\text{id}).$$

This yields that

$$a_n(\text{id}) \lesssim \frac{1}{n^{\alpha/\lambda} \psi(n^{1/\lambda})} \lesssim e_n(\text{id}).$$

Using now [10, Theorem 3.3] we conclude the wanted result. \square

The following lemma will be useful in our later considerations.

Lemma 4.4. *If $(X; A_n)$ is a linear approximation scheme then $(X_q^b; A_n)$ is linear as well.*

Proof. We may assume that X is p -normed with $0 < p < q$. Let $1/p = 1/q + 1/s$. Since $(X; A_n)$ is linear there exist a sequence (P_n) of projections on X and $M > 0$ such that $\|P_n\|_{X,X} \leq M$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Next we show that this sequence is also uniformly bounded on X_q^b . Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Given $f \in X_q^b$ we choose a representation $f = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} g_j$ with $g_j \in A_{n(j)}$ and

$$\left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\varphi(j) \|g_j\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q} \leq 2 \|f\|_{X_q^b}^* \leq c \|f\|_{X_q^b}.$$

Let $j_0 \in \mathbb{N}_0$ be such that $n(j_0) \leq n < n(j_0+1)$. Then we consider the decomposition of $P_n f$ given by

$$P_n f = \sum_{j=0}^{j_0} g_j + \sum_{j=j_0+1}^{\infty} P_n g_j.$$

Applying Theorem 2.2 we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|P_n f\|_{X_q^b}^q &\lesssim \sum_{j=0}^{j_0} \varphi(j)^q \|g_j\|_X^q + \varphi(j_0+1)^q \left\| \sum_{j=j_0+1}^{\infty} P_n g_j \right\|_X^q \\
 &\leq \sum_{j=0}^{j_0} \varphi(j)^q \|g_j\|_X^q + \varphi(j_0+1)^q \left(\sum_{j=j_0+1}^{\infty} \|P_n g_j\|_X^p \right)^{q/p} \\
 &\leq \sum_{j=0}^{j_0} \varphi(j)^q \|g_j\|_X^q + M^q \varphi(j_0+1)^q \left(\sum_{j=j_0+1}^{\infty} \|g_j\|_X^p \right)^{q/p} \\
 &\leq \sum_{j=0}^{j_0} \varphi(j)^q \|g_j\|_X^q \\
 &\quad + M^q \varphi(j_0+1)^q \sum_{j=j_0+1}^{\infty} \varphi(j)^q \|g_j\|_X^q \left(\sum_{j=j_0+1}^{\infty} \varphi(j)^{-s} \right)^{q/s} \\
 &\leq \sum_{j=0}^{j_0} \varphi(j)^q \|g_j\|_X^q + M^q (1 - K_1^{-s})^{-q/s} \sum_{j=j_0+1}^{\infty} \varphi(j)^q \|g_j\|_X^q \\
 &\leq (1 + M^q (1 - K_1^{-s})^{-q/s}) c^q \|f\|_{X_q^b}^q
 \end{aligned}$$

where for the penultimate inequality we applied (3). This proves that (P_n) is uniformly bounded on X_q^b . \square

Corollary 4.5. *Assume that $(X; A_n)$ is a linear approximation scheme satisfying (13) and let $0 < \alpha_1 < \alpha_0$ and $0 < q_0, q_1 \leq \infty$. Then for the embedding $\text{id} : X_{q_0}^{\alpha_0} \hookrightarrow X_{q_1}^{\alpha_1}$ we have*

$$a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim n^{-(\alpha_0 - \alpha_1)/\lambda}.$$

Proof. According to (7) we have that

$$X_{q_0}^{\alpha_0} = (X_{q_1}^{\alpha_1})_{q_0}^{\alpha_0 - \alpha_1}.$$

Note that by Lemma 4.4 the approximation scheme $(X_{q_1}^{\alpha_1}; A_n)$ is also linear and hence, the result follows from Corollary 4.3. \square

Since $(X_q^{(0,\gamma)})_p^\alpha = X_p^{(\alpha, \gamma+1/q)}$ if $\gamma > -1/q$ (see [8, Theorem 3.2]), we can also derive the following.

Corollary 4.6. *Assume that $(X; A_n)$ is a linear approximation scheme satisfying (13) and let $\alpha > 0, 0 < q_0, q_1 \leq \infty$ and $\gamma_1 > -1/q_1$. Then for the embedding $\text{id} : X_{q_0}^{(\alpha, \gamma_1+1/q_1)} \hookrightarrow X_{q_1}^{(0, \gamma_1)}$ we have*

$$a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim n^{-\alpha/\lambda}.$$

Corollary 4.7. *Let $0 < q \leq \infty, \gamma \geq -1/q$ and assume that $(X; A_n)$ is a linear approximation scheme satisfying (13). Then for the embedding $\text{id} : X_q^{(0, \gamma)} \hookrightarrow X$ we have:*

- (a) $a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim (\log n)^{-(\gamma+1/q)}$ if $\gamma > -1/q$,
- (b) $a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim (\log \log n)^{-1/q}$ if $\gamma = -1/q$ and $0 < q < \infty$.

Proof. Suppose first that $\gamma > -1/q$. By Example 2.4, we have $\varphi(j) = 2^{j(\gamma+1/q)}$ and $n(j) = \mu_j = 2^{2^j}$. Applying Theorem 4.2, we get

$$a_{[\mu_j^\lambda]_{+1}}(\text{id}) \lesssim (\log \mu_j)^{-(\gamma+1/q)} \lesssim e_{[\mu_j^\lambda]_{+1}}(\text{id}).$$

It follows that

$$a_n(\text{id}) \lesssim (\log n)^{-(\gamma+1/q)} \lesssim e_n(\text{id}).$$

Then [10, Theorem 3.3] yields the estimate (a).

If $\gamma = -1/q$ and $0 < q < \infty$, then $\varphi(j) = 2^{j/q}$ and $n(j) = \rho_j = 2^{\mu_j}$. By Theorem 4.2, we obtain

$$a_{[\rho_j^\lambda]_{+1}}(\text{id}) \lesssim (\log \log \rho_j)^{-1/q} \lesssim e_{[\rho_j^\lambda]_{+1}}(\text{id}).$$

This yields that

$$a_n(\text{id}) \lesssim (\log \log n)^{-1/q} \lesssim e_n(\text{id})$$

and so, applying again [10, Theorem 3.3], we derive that

$$a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim (\log \log n)^{-1/q}.$$

□

Taking into account Lemma 4.4 we can combine Corollary 4.7 with the reiteration formula (8) to obtain the following result.

Corollary 4.8. *Let $0 < q_0, q_1 \leq \infty$ and $\gamma_0, \gamma_1 \in \mathbb{R}$ with $\gamma_0 + 1/q_0 > \gamma_1 + 1/q_1 > 0$. If $(X; A_n)$ is a linear approximation scheme satisfying (13), then for the embedding $\text{id} : X_{q_0}^{(0, \gamma_0)} \hookrightarrow X_{q_1}^{(0, \gamma_1)}$ we have*

$$a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim (\log n)^{-(\gamma_0 - \gamma_1 + 1/q_0 - 1/q_1)}.$$

Remark 4.9. Note that the estimates in Corollaries 4.7 and 4.8 do not depend on λ .

We close this section by analysing the degree of compactness of the embeddings from classical approximation spaces into limiting approximation spaces. Proofs are more involved due to the jumps in the scale and the lack of relationships among the parameters.

Theorem 4.10. *Let $0 < \alpha < \infty, 0 < u, q \leq \infty, \gamma + 1/q > 0$ and ψ is a slowly varying function. Assume that $(X; A_n)$ is a linear approximation scheme satisfying (13). Then for the embedding $\text{id} : X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)} \hookrightarrow X_q^{(0, \gamma)}$ we get*

$$a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim n^{-\alpha/\lambda} (\log n)^{\gamma+1/q} \psi(n^{1/\lambda})^{-1}.$$

Proof. Assume $0 < u, q < \infty$. According to Example 2.3, for the space $X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}$ we have $n(j) = 2^j$. Let $Q_0 = P_1$ and $Q_j = P_{2^j} - P_{2^{j-1}}, j \in \mathbb{N}$. Write also $n_\gamma(j) = \mu_j$ and $R_j = P_{n_\gamma(j)} - P_{n_\gamma(j-1)}, j \in \mathbb{N}$, with $R_0 = P_1$. Take $j, r \in \mathbb{N}$ with

$$(14) \quad 2^{r-2} < j \leq 2^{r-1}, \text{ so } \log j \sim r.$$

As $m(j) \sim n(j)^\lambda = 2^{j\lambda}$, there are positive numbers c_1, c_2 such that $c_1 2^{j\lambda} \leq m(j) \leq c_2 2^{j\lambda}$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} a_{[c_2 2^{j\lambda}]+1}(\text{id}) &\leq \|\text{id} - P_{n(j)}\|_{X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}, X_q^{(0, \gamma)}} = \left\| \text{id} - \sum_{k=0}^j Q_k \right\|_{X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}, X_q^{(0, \gamma)}} \\ &= \left\| \sum_{k=j+1}^{2^r} Q_k + \sum_{k>r} R_k \right\|_{X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}, X_q^{(0, \gamma)}} \\ &\leq c \left(\left\| \sum_{k=j+1}^{2^r} Q_k \right\|_{X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}, X_q^{(0, \gamma)}} + \left\| \sum_{k>r} R_k \right\|_{X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}, X_q^{(0, \gamma)}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Given any $f \in X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}$, since $\sum_{k=j+1}^{2^r} Q_k f \in A_{\mu_r}$, applying Theorem 2.2 to $X_q^{(0, \gamma)}$ where $\varphi(j) = 2^{j(\gamma+1/q)}$, we get that

$$\left\| \sum_{k=j+1}^{2^r} Q_k f \right\|_{X_q^{(0, \gamma)}} \lesssim 2^{(\gamma+1/q)r} \left\| \sum_{k=j+1}^{2^r} Q_k f \right\|_X.$$

In order to estimate the last term, we may assume without loss of generality that $\|\cdot\|_X$ is a p -norm with $0 < p < u$. Put $1/s = 1/p - 1/u$. We obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \sum_{k=j+1}^{2^r} Q_k f \right\|_X &\leq \left(\sum_{k=j+1}^{2^r} \|Q_k f\|_X^p \right)^{1/p} \\ &\leq \left(\sum_{k=j+1}^{2^r} (2^{k\alpha} \psi(2^k) \|Q_k f\|_X)^u \right)^{1/u} \left(\sum_{k=j+1}^{2^r} 2^{-k\alpha s} \psi(2^k)^{-s} \right)^{1/s} \\ &\lesssim 2^{-j\alpha} \psi(2^j)^{-1} \left(\sum_{k=j+1}^{2^r} (2^{k\alpha} \psi(2^k) \|Q_k f\|_X)^u \right)^{1/u} \\ &\lesssim 2^{-j\alpha} \psi(2^j)^{-1} \|f\|_{X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\left\| \sum_{k=j+1}^{2^r} Q_k \right\|_{X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}, X_q^{(0, \gamma)}} \lesssim 2^{(\gamma+1/q)r} 2^{-j\alpha} \psi(2^j)^{-1} \sim j^{\gamma+1/q} 2^{-j\alpha} \psi(2^j)^{-1}.$$

On the other hand,

$$\begin{aligned} \|R_k f\|_X &= \left\| \sum_{\nu=2^{k-1}+1}^{2^k} Q_\nu f \right\|_X \leq \left(\sum_{\nu=2^{k-1}+1}^{2^k} \|Q_\nu f\|_X^p \right)^{1/p} \\ &\leq \left(\sum_{\nu=2^{k-1}+1}^{2^k} (2^{\nu\alpha} \psi(2^\nu) \|Q_\nu f\|_X)^u \right)^{1/u} \left(\sum_{\nu=2^{k-1}+1}^{2^k} 2^{-\nu\alpha s} \psi(2^\nu)^{-s} \right)^{1/s} \\ &\lesssim 2^{-\alpha 2^{k-1}} \psi(2^{2^{k-1}})^{-1} \left(\sum_{\nu=2^{k-1}+1}^{2^k} (2^{\nu\alpha} \psi(2^\nu) \|Q_\nu f\|_X)^u \right)^{1/u}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, if $u \leq q$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\left\| \sum_{k>r} R_k f \right\|_{X_q^{(0,\gamma)}} &\lesssim \left(\sum_{k>r} (2^{k(\gamma+1/q)} \|R_k f\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q} \\
&\leq \left(\sum_{k>r} (2^{k(\gamma+1/q)} \|R_k f\|_X)^u \right)^{1/u} \\
&\lesssim \left(\sum_{k>r} 2^{k(\gamma+1/q)u} 2^{-\alpha u 2^{k-1}} \psi(2^{2^{k-1}})^{-u} \sum_{\nu=2^{k-1}+1}^{2^k} (2^{\nu\alpha} \psi(2^\nu) \|Q_\nu f\|_X)^u \right)^{1/u} \\
&\lesssim 2^{r(\gamma+1/q)} 2^{-\alpha 2^{r-1}} \psi(2^{2^{r-1}})^{-1} \left(\sum_{k>r} \sum_{\nu=2^{k-1}+1}^{2^k} (2^{\nu\alpha} \psi(2^\nu) \|Q_\nu f\|_X)^u \right)^{1/u} \\
&\lesssim j^{\gamma+1/q} 2^{-j\alpha} \psi(2^j)^{-1} \|f\|_{X_u^{(\alpha,\psi)}}
\end{aligned}$$

where in the last inequality we have used (14) and Theorem 4.1.

If $q < u$, then $\rho = u/q > 1$. Let $1/\rho + 1/\rho' = 1$. By Hölder inequality we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\left\| \sum_{k>r} R_k f \right\|_{X_q^{(0,\gamma)}} &\lesssim \left(\sum_{k>r} (2^{k(\gamma+1/q)} \|R_k f\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q} \\
&\lesssim \left(\sum_{k>r} \left(2^{k(\gamma+1/q)u} 2^{-\alpha 2^{k-1}u} \psi(2^{2^{k-1}})^{-u} \sum_{\nu=2^{k-1}+1}^{2^k} (2^{\nu\alpha} \psi(2^\nu) \|Q_\nu f\|_X)^u \right)^{q/u} \right)^{1/q} \\
&\leq \left(\sum_{k>r} \sum_{\nu=2^{k-1}+1}^{2^k} (2^{\nu\alpha} \psi(2^\nu) \|Q_\nu f\|_X)^u \right)^{1/u} \\
&\quad \times \left(\sum_{k>r} \left(2^{k(\gamma+1/q)} 2^{-\alpha 2^{k-1}} \psi(2^{2^{k-1}})^{-1} \right)^{q\rho'} \right)^{1/q\rho'} \\
&\lesssim 2^{r(\gamma+1/q)} 2^{-\alpha 2^{r-1}} \psi(2^{2^{r-1}})^{-1} \|f\|_{X_u^{(\alpha,\psi)}} \\
&\lesssim j^{\gamma+1/q} 2^{-j\alpha} \psi(2^j)^{-1} \|f\|_{X_u^{(\alpha,\psi)}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Consequently, for any $0 < q, u < \infty$, it follows that $a_{[c_2 2^{j\lambda}]_+ 1}(\text{id}) \lesssim j^{\gamma+1/q} 2^{-j\alpha} \psi(2^j)^{-1}$, which yields that

$$(15) \quad a_n(\text{id}) \lesssim n^{-\alpha/\lambda} (\log n)^{\gamma+1/q} \psi(n^{1/\lambda})^{-1}.$$

Next we establish the lower estimate for entropy numbers. Let $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ with $c_1 2^{k_0\lambda} - c_2 > 0$. Take any $r \in \mathbb{N}$ and let $j \in \mathbb{N}$ be such that

$$(16) \quad j = 2^r + k_0.$$

Let $Y = \{g \in A_{2^j} : P_{\mu_r} g = 0\} = \ker(P_{\mu_r} : A_{2^j} \rightarrow A_{2^j})$. Since

$$A_{\mu_r} = P_{\mu_r} A_{\mu_r} \subseteq P_{\mu_r} A_{2^j} \subseteq P_{\mu_r} X = A_{\mu_r},$$

we have that $P_{\mu_r} : A_{2^j} \rightarrow A_{2^j}$ has rank $\dim A_{\mu_r}$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \dim A_{2^j} &= \dim [\ker(P_{\mu_r} : A_{2^j} \rightarrow A_{2^j})] + \text{rank} [P_{\mu_r} : A_{2^j} \rightarrow A_{2^j}] \\ &= \dim Y + \dim A_{\mu_r}. \end{aligned}$$

Using (16), we get

$$\dim Y \geq c_1 2^{j\lambda} - c_2 \mu_r^\lambda = 2^{(j-k_0)\lambda} (c_1 2^{k_0\lambda} - c_2) \sim 2^{j\lambda}.$$

By volume arguments (see [6, (1.1.10), p. 9]), we derive

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &\lesssim 2^{([2^{j\lambda}] - 1) / \dim Y} e_{[2^{j\lambda}]}(\text{id} : Y \rightarrow Y) \\ &\lesssim e_{[2^{j\lambda}]}(\text{id} : Y \rightarrow Y). \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, since $(\text{id} - P_{\mu_r})g = g$ for any $g \in Y$, the following commutative diagram holds

$$\begin{array}{ccc} Y & \xrightarrow{\text{id}} & Y \\ \text{id} \downarrow & & \uparrow \text{id} - P_{\mu_r} \\ X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)} & \xrightarrow{\text{id}} & X_q^{(0, \gamma)} \end{array}$$

It follows that

$$1 \lesssim \|\text{id}\|_{Y, X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}} e_{[2^{j\lambda}]}(\text{id} : X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)} \hookrightarrow X_q^{(0, \gamma)}) \|\text{id} - P_{\mu_r}\|_{X_q^{(0, \gamma)}, Y}.$$

We now proceed to estimate the norms of the two operators. By Theorem 2.2, given any $f \in Y \subseteq A_{2^j}$ we obtain

$$\|f\|_{X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}} \lesssim \|f\|_{X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}}^* \leq 2^{j\alpha} \psi(2^j) \|f\|_X.$$

Whence $\|\text{id}\|_{Y, X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)}} \lesssim 2^{j\alpha} \psi(2^j)$. As for the other operator, given any $f \in X_q^{(0, \gamma)}$, using that $\|\cdot\|_X$ is a p -norm with $1/p = 1/q + 1/s$ and Theorem 4.1, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|(\text{id} - P_{\mu_r})f\|_X &= \left\| \left(\text{id} - \sum_{k=0}^r R_k \right) f \right\|_X = \left\| \sum_{k=r+1}^{\infty} R_k f \right\|_X \\ &\leq \left(\sum_{k=r+1}^{\infty} (2^{(\gamma+1/q)k} \|R_k f\|_X)^q \right)^{1/q} \left(\sum_{k=r+1}^{\infty} 2^{-(\gamma+1/q)sk} \right)^{1/s} \\ &\lesssim 2^{-(\gamma+1/q)r} \|f\|_{X_q^{(0, \gamma)}} \\ &\lesssim j^{-(\gamma+1/q)} \|f\|_{X_q^{(0, \gamma)}}. \end{aligned}$$

So, $\|\text{id} - P_{\mu_r}\|_{X_q^{(0, \gamma)}, X} \lesssim j^{-(\gamma+1/q)}$. This yields that $e_{[2^{j\lambda}]}(\text{id}) \gtrsim 2^{-j\alpha} \psi(2^j)^{-1} j^{\gamma+1/q}$ and therefore

$$(17) \quad e_n(\text{id}) \gtrsim n^{-\alpha/\lambda} \psi(n^{1/\lambda})^{-1} (\log n)^{\gamma+1/q}.$$

Finally, by (15), (17) and [10, Theorem 3.3], we conclude that

$$a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim n^{-\alpha/\lambda} \psi(n^{1/\lambda})^{-1} (\log n)^{\gamma+1/q}.$$

The cases $q = \infty$ and/or $u = \infty$ can be treated similarly. □

Remark 4.11. In the particular case that we take $\psi(t) = (1 + |\log t|)^{\gamma+1/q}$, $t > 0$, in Theorem 4.10 we recover Corollary 4.6.

The techniques used in the proof of Theorem 4.10 may be modified to deal with the limit case $\gamma = -1/q$ where there is another jump in the scale. Instead of R_j we should work with $S_j = P_{\rho_j} - P_{\rho_{j-1}}$ and the space Y should be defined as the collection of all $g \in A_{2^j}$ such that $P_{\rho_r} g = 0$. The result reads as follows.

Theorem 4.12. *Let $0 < \alpha < \infty, 0 < u \leq \infty, 0 < q < \infty$ and ψ is a slowly varying function. Assume that $(X; A_n)$ is a linear approximation scheme satisfying (13). Then for the embedding $\text{id} : X_u^{(\alpha, \psi)} \hookrightarrow X_q^{(0, -1/q)}$ we have*

$$a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim n^{-\alpha/\lambda} (\log \log n)^{1/q} \psi(n^{1/\lambda})^{-1}.$$

5. APPLICATIONS TO BESOV SPACES

Let $d \in \mathbb{N}$. We write \mathbb{T}^d for the d -torus

$$\mathbb{T}^d = \{x = (x_1, \dots, x_d) \in \mathbb{R}^d : |x_j| \leq \pi \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, d\}.$$

We identify points x, y if $x - y = 2k\pi$ for any $k \in \mathbb{Z}^d$.

For $1 < p < \infty$, let $L_p = L_p(\mathbb{T}^d)$ be the usual Lebesgue space on \mathbb{T}^d . For $s \geq 0, 0 < q \leq \infty$ and ψ a slowly varying function, $B_{p,q}^{s,\psi}$ stands for the Besov space formed by all $f \in L_p$ having a finite quasi-norm

$$\|f\|_{B_{p,q}^{s,\psi}} = \|f\|_{L_p} + \left(\int_0^1 (t^{-s} \psi(t) \omega_k(f, t)_p)^q \frac{dt}{t} \right)^{1/q}$$

(with the usual modification if $q = \infty$). Here $s < k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\omega_k(f, t)_p$ is the k -th order modulus of smoothness of f , given by

$$\omega_k(f, t)_p = \sup_{|h| \leq t} \|\Delta_h^k f\|_{L_p}, t > 0,$$

where

$$\Delta_h^1 f(x) = f(x+h) - f(x) \text{ and } \Delta_h^{k+1} f(x) = \Delta_h^1(\Delta_h^k f)(x).$$

Note that the case $\psi(t) = 1$ and $s > 0$ corresponds to the classical periodic Besov spaces $B_{p,q}^s$ defined by differences. If $s = 0$ and $\psi(t) = (1 + |\log t|)^\gamma$, we simply write $B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma}$.

Let $T_0 = \{0\}$ and for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let

$$T_n = \left\{ \sum_{\sum_{j=1}^d |k_j| \leq n} c_k e^{ik \cdot x} : c_k \in \mathbb{C}, k = (k_1, \dots, k_d) \in \mathbb{Z}^d \right\}$$

be the linear space of all trigonometric polynomials of (triangular) degree less than or equal to n . Here $k \cdot x = k_1 x_1 + \dots + k_d x_d$. Consider also the sets of all trigonometric polynomials of cubic (respectively, spherical) degree less than or equal to n given by $R_0 = S_0 = \{0\}$ and

$$R_n = \left\{ \sum_{\max_{j=1, \dots, d} |k_j| \leq n} c_k e^{ik \cdot x} : c_k \in \mathbb{C}, k = (k_1, \dots, k_d) \in \mathbb{Z}^d \right\}$$

and

$$S_n = \left\{ \sum_{(\sum_{j=1}^d |k_j|^2)^{1/2} \leq n} c_k e^{ik \cdot x} : c_k \in \mathbb{C}, k = (k_1, \dots, k_d) \in \mathbb{Z}^d \right\}.$$

It is clear that if $d = 1$ then $T_n = R_n = S_n$. It is worth mentioning that in multivariate approximation the index set where frequencies of the polynomials come from plays an important role because some results depend on the chosen restriction for the frequencies (see, for example, [20] and [40]). We have

$$T_n \subseteq R_n \subseteq T_{dn}, T_n \subseteq S_n \subseteq T_{dn}.$$

For $J_n = T_n, R_n, S_n$ put

$$E_n^J(f) = \inf\{\|f - g\|_{L_p} : g \in J_n\}.$$

Let $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $d < 2^{k_0}$. We have $E_{2^j+k_0}^T(f) \leq E_{2^j}^R(f) \leq E_{2^j}^T(f)$ and $E_{2^j+k_0}^T(f) \leq E_{2^j}^S(f) \leq E_{2^j}^T(f)$. Therefore, if $s > 0$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_{(L_p; R_n)_q^{(s, \psi)}}^\diamond &= \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (2^{js} \psi(2^j) E_{2^j}^R(f))^q \right)^{1/q} \\ &\leq \|f\|_{(L_p; T_n)_q^{(s, \psi)}}^\diamond \\ &\lesssim \left(\|f\|_{L_p}^q + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (2^{js} \psi(2^j) E_{2^j+k_0}^T(f))^q \right)^{1/q} \\ &\lesssim \|f\|_{(L_p; R_n)_q^{(s, \psi)}}^\diamond. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $(L_p; T_n)_q^{(s, \psi)} = (L_p; S_n)_q^{(s, \psi)}$ and $(L_p; T_n)_q^{(0, \gamma)} = (L_p; R_n)_q^{(0, \gamma)} = (L_p; S_n)_q^{(0, \gamma)}$.

Note also that $(L_p; R_n)$ is a linear approximation scheme with

$$(P_n f)(x) = \sum_{|k_j| \leq n} \widehat{f}(k) e^{ik \cdot x} \text{ and } \widehat{f}(k) = (2\pi)^{-d} \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} f(x) e^{-ik \cdot x} dx, k \in \mathbb{Z}^d,$$

(see [20, Corollary 3.5.2 and Theorem 3.5.7]). Moreover, $\dim R_n = (2n + 1)^d$, so (13) is satisfied.

When $\psi(t) = 1$ and $s > 0$, it is known that $B_{p,q}^s = (L_p; R_n)_q^s$ (see [30, 5.3] and also [37, Corollary 3.7.1]). On the other hand, if $d = 1$ and $\psi(t) = (1 + |\log t|)^\gamma$, it is shown in [16, Corollary 7.1/(i)] that $B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma} = (L_p; R_n)_q^{(0,\gamma)}$. In fact, using Jackson and Bernstein inequalities (see [30, 38]) and a convenient form of the Hardy inequality, for $d \in \mathbb{N}$, if $s > 0$ and ψ is a slowly varying function, then $B_{p,q}^{s,\psi} = (L_p; R_n)_q^b$ where $b = (n^s \psi(n))$, and if $\gamma \geq -1/q$, then $B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma} = (L_p; R_n)_q^{(0,\gamma)}$ (see [36]; see also [7, Lemma 2.1]). Therefore, as a direct consequence of Corollaries 4.3 to 4.8, we derive the following results.

Corollary 5.1. *Let $1 < p < \infty, 0 < q \leq \infty, s > 0$ and let ψ be a slowly varying function. Then for the embedding $\text{id} : B_{p,q}^{s,\psi} \hookrightarrow L_p$ we have*

$$a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim \frac{1}{n^{s/d} \psi(n^{1/d})}.$$

Corollary 5.2. *Let $1 < p < \infty, 0 < q_0, q_1 \leq \infty$ and $0 < s_1 < s_0$. Then for the embedding $\text{id} : B_{p,q_0}^{s_0} \hookrightarrow B_{p,q_1}^{s_1}$ we have*

$$a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim n^{-(s_0-s_1)/d}.$$

Corollary 5.3. *Let $1 < p < \infty, 0 < q \leq \infty$ and $\gamma \geq -1/q$. Then for the embedding $\text{id} : B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma} \hookrightarrow L_p$ we have:*

- (a) $a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim (\log n)^{-(\gamma+1/q)}$ if $\gamma > -1/q$.
 (b) $a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim (\log \log n)^{-1/q}$ if $\gamma = -1/q$ and $0 < q < \infty$.

Corollary 5.4. *Let $1 < p < \infty, 0 < q_0, q_1 \leq \infty$ and $\gamma_0, \gamma_1 \in \mathbb{R}$ with $\gamma_0 + 1/q_0 > \gamma_1 + 1/q_1 > 0$. Then for the embedding $\text{id} : B_{p,q_0}^{0,\gamma_0} \hookrightarrow B_{p,q_1}^{0,\gamma_1}$ we have*

$$a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim (\log n)^{-(\gamma_0 - \gamma_1 + 1/q_0 - 1/q_1)}.$$

Remark 5.5. It should be noticed that the asymptotic behaviours described in Corollaries 5.3 and 5.4 are independent of the dimension d . Moreover, the fine index q is involved in the estimates which is not the case in Corollaries 5.1 and 5.2.

Corollary 5.6. *Let $1 < p < \infty, s > 0, 0 < q_0, q_1 \leq \infty$ and $\gamma > -1/q_1$. Then for the embedding $\text{id} : B_{p,q_0}^{s,\gamma+1/q_1} \hookrightarrow B_{p,q_1}^{0,\gamma}$ we have*

$$a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim n^{-s/d}.$$

We complete the paper with the following consequence of Theorems 4.10 and 4.12. In particular, we are able to extend Corollary 5.6 to the full range of parameters.

Corollary 5.7. *Let $1 < p < \infty, s > 0, 0 < u, q \leq \infty, \gamma \geq -1/q$ and let ψ be a slowly varying function. Then for the embedding $\text{id} : B_{p,u}^{s,\psi} \hookrightarrow B_{p,q}^{0,\gamma}$ we obtain:*

- (a) $a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim n^{-s/d} (\log n)^{\gamma+1/q} \psi(n^{1/d})^{-1}$ if $\gamma > -1/q$.
 (b) $a_n(\text{id}) \sim e_n(\text{id}) \sim n^{-s/d} (\log \log n)^{1/q} \psi(n^{1/d})^{-1}$ if $\gamma = -1/q$ and $0 < q < \infty$.

REFERENCES

- [1] Almira, J.M., Luther, U.: Compactness and generalized approximation spaces. *Numer. Funct. Anal. Optim.* **23**, 1–38 (2002)
- [2] Almira, J.M., Luther, U.: Generalized approximation spaces and applications. *Math. Nachr.* **263**, 3–35 (2004)
- [3] Bingham, N.H., Goldie, C.M., Teugels, J.L.: *Regular Variation*. Encyclopedia in Mathematics and its Applications, vol. 27, Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge (1987)
- [4] Butzer, P.L., Scherer, K.: *Approximationsprozesse und Interpolationsmethoden*. Mannheim, Zürich (1968)
- [5] Caetano, A.M., Gogatishvili, A., Opic, B.: Sharp embeddings of Besov spaces involving only logarithmic smoothness. *J. Approx. Theory* **152**, 188–214 (2008)
- [6] Carl, B., Stephani, I.: *Entropy, Compactness and the Approximation of Operators*. Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge (1990)
- [7] Cobos, F., Domínguez, O.: Embeddings of Besov spaces of logarithmic smoothness. *Studia Math.* **223**, 193–204 (2014)
- [8] Cobos, F., Domínguez, O.: Approximation spaces, limiting interpolation and Besov spaces. *J. Approx. Theory* **189**, 43–66 (2015)
- [9] Cobos, F., Domínguez, O.: On Besov spaces of logarithmic smoothness and Lipschitz spaces. *J. Math. Anal. Appl.* **425**, 71–84 (2015)
- [10] Cobos, F., Kühn, T.: Approximation and entropy numbers in Besov spaces of generalized smoothness. *J. Approx. Theory* **160**, 56–70 (2009)
- [11] Cobos, F., Milman, M.: On a limit class of approximation spaces. *Numer. Funct. Anal. Optim.* **11**, 11–31 (1990)
- [12] Cobos, F., Resina, I.: Representation theorems for some operator ideals. *J. London Math. Soc.* **39**, 324–334 (1989)
- [13] Cobos, F., Resina, I.: On some operator ideals defined by approximation numbers. In: *Geometric Aspects of Banach Spaces*, London Math. Soc. Lecture Note Ser., vol. 140, Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge (1989), pp. 133–139
- [14] DeVore, R.A., Lorentz, G.G.: *Constructive Approximation*. Springer, Berlin (1993)

- [15] DeVore, R.A., Popov, V.A.: Interpolation of approximation spaces. In: Constructive Function Theory, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia (1988), pp. 110–119
- [16] DeVore, R.A., Riemenschneider, S.D., Sharpley, R.C.: Weak interpolation in Banach spaces. *J. Funct. Anal.* **33**, 58–94 (1979)
- [17] Edmunds, D.E., Evans, W.D.: *Hardy Operators, Function Spaces and Embeddings*. Springer, Berlin (2004)
- [18] Edmunds, D.E., Triebel, H.: *Function Spaces, Entropy Numbers, Differential Operators*. Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge (1996)
- [19] Fehér, F., Grössler, G.: On an extremal scale of approximation spaces. *J. Comput. Anal. Appl.* **3**, 95–108 (2001)
- [20] Grafakos, L.: *Classical Fourier Analysis*. Springer, New York (2008)
- [21] Haroske, D.D., Skrzypczak, L.: Entropy and approximation numbers of embeddings of function spaces with Muckenhoupt weights, I. *Rev. Mat. Complut.* **21**, 135–177 (2008)
- [22] Haroske, D.D., Skrzypczak, L.: Entropy and approximation numbers of embeddings of function spaces with Muckenhoupt weights, II. General weights. *Ann. Acad. Scient. Fennicae Math.* **36**, 111–138 (2011)
- [23] Haroske, D.D., Triebel, H.: Wavelet bases and entropy numbers in weighted function spaces. *Math. Nachr.* **278**, 108–132 (2005)
- [24] König, H.: *Eigenvalue Distribution of Compact Operators*. Birkhäuser, Basel (1986)
- [25] Köthe, G.: *Topological Vector Spaces I*. Springer, Berlin (1983)
- [26] Kühn, T., Leopold, H.-G., Sickel, W., Skrzypczak, L.: Entropy numbers of embeddings of weighted Besov spaces. *Constr. Approx.* **23**, 61–77 (2006)
- [27] Kühn, T., Leopold, H.-G., Sickel, W., Skrzypczak, L.: Entropy numbers of embeddings of weighted Besov spaces II. *Proc. Edinburgh Math. Soc.* **49**, 331–359 (2006)
- [28] Kühn, T., Leopold, H.-G., Sickel, W., Skrzypczak, L.: Entropy numbers of embeddings of weighted Besov spaces III. Weights of logarithmic type. *Math. Z.* **255**, 1–15 (2007)
- [29] Leopold, H.-G.: Embeddings and entropy numbers in Besov spaces of generalized smoothness. In: *Function Spaces, Lecture Notes in Pure and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 213, Marcel Dekker, New York (2000), pp. 323–336
- [30] Nikolskiĭ, S.M.: *Approximation of Functions of Several Variables and Imbedding Theorems*. Springer, Berlin (1975)
- [31] Peetre, J., Sparr, G.: Interpolation of normed abelian groups. *Ann. Mat. Pura Appl.* **92**, 217–262 (1972)
- [32] Petrushev, P.P., Popov, V.A.: *Rational Approximation of Real Functions*. *Encyclopedia of Mathematics and its Applications*, vol. 28, Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge (1987)
- [33] Pietsch, A.: *Operator Ideals*. North-Holland, Amsterdam (1980)
- [34] Pietsch, A.: Approximation spaces. *J. Approx. Theory* **32**, 115–134 (1981)
- [35] Pustylnik, E.: Ultrasymmetric sequence spaces in approximation theory. *Collect. Math.* **57**, 257–277 (2006)
- [36] Schmeisser, H.-J., Runovski, K.: in preparation
- [37] Schmeisser, H.-J., Triebel, H.: *Topics in Fourier Analysis and Function Spaces*. Wiley, Chichester (1987)
- [38] Temlyakov, V.N.: *Approximation of Periodic Functions*. Nova Science, New York (1994)
- [39] Triebel, H.: *Interpolation Theory, Function Spaces, Differential Operators*. North-Holland, Amsterdam (1978)
- [40] Weisz, F.: ℓ_1 -summability of d -dimensional Fourier transforms. *Constr. Approx.* **34**, 421–452 (2011)

¹ DEPARTAMENTO DE ANÁLISIS MATEMÁTICO, FACULTAD DE MATEMÁTICAS, UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID, PLAZA DE CIENCIAS 3, 28040 MADRID, SPAIN
E-mail address: `cobos@mat.ucm.es`

² DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, CENTER FOR MATHEMATICS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF COIMBRA (CMUC), 3001-454 COIMBRA, PORTUGAL
E-mail address: `oscar.dominguez@mat.uc.pt`

³ MATHEMATISCHES INSTITUT, UNIVERSITÄT LEIPZIG, AUGUSTUSPLATZ 10, 04109 LEIPZIG, GERMANY
E-mail address: `kuehn@math.uni-leipzig.de`